

**A SYSTEMATIC STUDY AND BIOECOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS
OF THE GENUS *ARABIDOPSIS* (DC.) HEYNH. IN THE FLORA OF THE NAKHCHIVAN
AUTONOMOUS REPUBLIC**

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**ФЛОРА НАХЧЫВАНСКОЙ АВТОНОМНОЙ РЕСПУБЛИКИ
ARABIDOPSIS (DC.) HEYNH. СИСТЕМАТИЧЕСКИЙ ОБЗОР
И БИОЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ**

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Abstract

Arabidopsis (DC.) Heynh. is included in the flora of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic based on the results of research conducted in 2023-2024 and literature data. The species composition of the genus was examined and taxonomic analysis was made. [*Arabidopsis parvula* (Schrenk) O.E. Schulz and *Arabidopsis thaliana* (L.) Heynh.] is widespread. The morphological features and general distribution regions of the species included in the genus were examined. It was determined that the species included in the genus are distributed in the autonomous republic from pastures to the middle mountain belt. *Arabidopsis* (DC.) Heynh is distributed in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. geographical types of the species were examined, the plant groups formed by them were examined.

Аннотация

Arabidopsis (DC.) Heynh. включен во флору Нахчыванской Автономной Республики на основании результатов исследований, проведенных в 2023-2024 годах, и литературных данных. Изучен видовой состав рода и проведен таксономический анализ. [*Arabidopsis parvula* (Schrenk) O.E. Schulz и *Arabidopsis thaliana* (L.) Heynh.] широко распространен. Изучены морфологические особенности и общие регионы распространения видов, входящих в род. Определено, что виды, входящие в род, распространены в автономной республике от пастбищ до среднего горного пояса. *Arabidopsis* (DC.) Heynh. распространен в Нахчыванской Автономной Республике. Изучены географические типы видов, изучены образуемые ими растительные группировки.

Keywords: Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, *Arabidopsis*, *Arabidopsis parvula*, *Arabidopsis thaliana*, systematic review.

Ключевые слова: Нахчыванской Автономной Республике, *Arabidopsis*, *Arabidopsis parvula*, *Arabidopsis thaliana*, систематический обзор.

Introduction. Among natural resources, flora has a special importance due to its position in the ecosystem and the beginning of the food chain. It is known that in solving the socio-economic problems of each country, it is important to fulfill a number of complex tasks, such as effective use of vegetation, state control over their protection, identification and protection of rare species. *Arabidopsis* (DC.) Heynh is one of the plants that play an important role in the formation and formation of flora in the territory of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, belonging to the *Brassicaceae* Burnet family. species included in the genus.

Materials and methodology. The object of research was the territory of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. The materials are *Arabidopsis*

(DC.) Heynh, collected during expeditions to the regions of the Autonomous Republic from the middle mountain belt to the middle mountain belt. species of the genus were taken. In determining the species, Grossheim A.A. "Flora Kavkaza", Grossheim A.A. "Flora Azerbaijan" [5, 6], "Conspekt Flora Kavkaza" [1], as well as works and methodological instructions of Azerbaijani botanists were used.

The latest taxonomic additions and changes to the International Code of Botanical Nomenclature "APG" and "World of Plants" were made according to the works of T.H. Talybov, A.Ş. Ibrahimov "Taxonomic spectrum of the Nakhchivan flora", E.M. Gurbanov "Systematics of Higher Plants" and A.M. Asgarov "Plant World of Azerbaijan" [3, 4, 7, 9,10, 11].

The studies of J. Portenier were taken as basis in determining the geographical elements of the species and determining its areal types [8].

Discussion of the research results. According to the literature *Arabidopsis* (DC.) Heynh. In the works "Flora Azerbaijan" and "Flora Kavkaz" it is stated that 13 species are included. However, during the molecular study of the genetic structure of the genus it was determined that some species were included in other genera *Arabidopsis* (DC.) Heynh, in the "Abstract of Flora Kavkaz" [5, 6, 7]. Being a part of the genus, *Arabidopsis pumila* (Steph.) N. Busch, taking into account its characteristics, was included in the genus *Thellungiella*. Thus, the study showed that 12 species belonging to the genus are distributed in the Caucasus territory *Arabidopsis* (DC.) Heynh. genus is represented by 12 species [1, 2]. Based on the studies and literature data *Arabidopsis* (DC.) Heynh. 12 species of the genus are distributed in the Caucasus, 2 species (*Arabidopsis parvula* (Schrenk) O.E. Schulz., *Arabidopsis thaliana* (L.) Heynh.) are distributed in Azerbaijan, including the territory of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic.

Arabidopsis parvula (Schrenk) O.E. Schultz in the Herbarium Fund of the Institute of Biological Resources of the Ministry of Science and Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan. It was determined that the herbarium copy of the species was first collected in the Caucasus on 26.05.1933 by T.S. Qederman from the vicinity of the village of Boyukduz, Kangarli district of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic [1, 2].

Arabidopsis (DC.) Heynh. It was determined that 2 species of the genus are distributed. The taxonomic spectrum of the genus in the local flora can be given as follows [3, 4, 10, 11]:

Familia: *Brassicaceae* Burnett, nom. cons. (= *Cruciferae* Juss., nom. cons.)

Genus: *Arabidopsis* (DC.) Heynh. - Kəsəkotu

1. *Arabidopsis parvula* (Schrenk) O.E. Schulz

2. *Arabidopsis thaliana* (L.) Heynh.

Arabidopsis (DC.) Heynh. The flower petals of the species included in the genus are mostly spiny, white or pale yellow. The ovary in plants is sessile and the stamen has a flat head. Its fruits are short-stalked, thin-skinned, annual herbaceous plants. The main distinguishing feature of the species is the color of the petals and whether the plant surface is covered with hairs or bare. *Arabidopsis* (DC.) Heynh. The species included in the genus are distributed in most regions of the autonomous republic, from the plains to the central mountain belt.

Arabidopsis parvula (Schrenk) O.E. Schulz type is an annual plant with a hairless, thin stem, 3-15 cm tall. The leaves at the bottom of the stem are elongated, while the leaves at the top are linear and lathed. Sepals are 1-2 mm long and linear in shape. The leaves are yellow, the stems are 3-6 cm long and erect. The plant flowers in April-May and fruits in May-June. The plant grows in lowland areas where there are very salty gravels. It is included in the Samrat geographical type.

Arabidopsis parvula (Schrenk) O.E. Schulz type was first collected in the Caucasus on 26.V.1933 in the

vicinity of Boyukduz village of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic [5].

As a result of our research in 2023-2024 *Arabidopsis parvula* (Schrenk) O.E. The Schulz type was collected by us from the Chalkhangala region of Kangarli district as a new distribution area. This species is also found in saline areas in Culfa, Ordubad and Shahbuz regions.

Arabidopsis thaliana (L.) Heynh. It is an annual plant with a stem covered with thin, simple or branched hairs, leaves with oblong-lanceolate, toothed edges, 4-40 cm tall. The leaves in the rosette group at the bottom of the stem are small, short-petiolate, almost stemless on the stem. The leaves are 3-4 mm long and white. The flower stalks are thin and straight. The plant flowers in March-April and bears fruit in April-May. The plant grows on stony cliffs, bushes, gravelly river banks and barren lands from the plains to the middle mountain belt. *Arabidopsis thaliana* (L.) Heynh. The species belongs to the West-Paleoartic geographical type [1, 7, 8].

Arabidopsis thaliana (L.) Heynh, in Azerbaijan. the species is found in almost all regions. In the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, it grows in Ordubad, Culfa, Shahbuz, Saderak and Babek regions.

Arabidopsis thaliana (L.) Heynh. The species was collected by us from the vicinity of Eylis village of Ordubad district, Ordubad city area, Alincechay coast of Culfa district, Yayıcı village, Nakhchivan city, Ayriñç, Ashagi Gishlaq villages of Shahbuz district.

To study the patterns of formation of complex phytocenoses in nature, the dynamics of plant groups should be studied first. Accordingly *Arabidopsis* (DC.) Heynh. was included in the flora of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic in the 2023-2024 research year. for the first time, the nature of the species of the genus, each of which will be placed in a separate vegetation type, was determined.

Arabidopsis parvula (Schrenk) O.E. Schulz Karagush mountain, Boyukduz village, Calhangala village of Kangarli district, Ayriñç, Kuku, Nursu, Bichenak villages of Shahbuz district, Ağdaban hill and subalpine meadows of Batabat district, Ebragunus and Arafsa villages of Culfa district, Paraga, Dirnis, Mazra villages of Ordubad are found alone or in different plant groups in the district. The formation of the plant in the meadow includes the following components: *Trifolium arvense*, *Trifolium pratense*, *Lotus corniculatus*, *Filipendula ulmaria*, *Ranunculus arvensis*, *Melilotus albus*, etc.

Arabidopsis thaliana (L.) Heynh. The presence of the plant in shrub and meadow formations in Arafsa village of Culfa district, Bichenak, Nursu, Ayriñç, Ashagi Kishlaq villages of Shahbuz district and Mazra, Pazmari, Unus, Aylis villages of Ordubad district were discovered by us. *Pyrethrum uniflorum*, *Trifolium pratense*, *Inula grandiflora*, *Senecio vernalis* were found in the plant group.

Conclusion. In our research conducted in 2023-2024 *Arabidopsis* (DC.) Heynh. systematic overview and bioecological characteristics were examined and the following results were obtained.

1. The species diversity of the *Arabidopsis* (DC.) Heynh. genus was investigated in the flora of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic and it was determined that 2 species [*Arabidopsis parvula* (Schrenk) O.E. Schulz and *Arabidopsis thaliana* (L.) Heynh.] were distributed. As a result of the research, the taxonomic spectrum of *Arabidopsis* (DC.) Heynh. was redrawn, the historical transformations of the taxa were analyzed.

2. *Arabidopsis* (DC.) Heynh was distributed in the territory of the autonomous republic. Geographical and areological analyzes of the genus were made and the geographical area types of the species were examined. It was determined that the plants belong to 2 geographical region types (Samrat and Western-Paleoartic).

3. *Arabidopsis* (DC.) Heynh is included in the local flora. The species of the genus are distributed in the regions from meadows to the middle mountain belt.

4. During the study, plant groups formed according to *Arabidopsis parvula* (Schrenk) O.E. Schulz and *Arabidopsis thaliana* (L.) Heynh. species were shown for the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic flora biodiversity.

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